

Appendix of Chemical Evolution of R-process Elements in Stars (CERES)

IV. An observational run-up of the third r-process peak with Hf, Os, Ir, and Pt

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1. Sensitivities and partial uncertainties for the individual Hf, Os, and Ir lines

In this section we present five tables with the uncertainties for each of the individual lines with measurements. The tables show the individual components of the total uncertainties of the abundances $A(X)$. In the case of the sensitivities to the atmospheric parameters we do not present an absolute value following a $\pm$ sign, but the behaviour of $A(X)$ with the variation of a particular atmospheric parameter – negative if abundance decreases with the increase in the value of the atmospheric parameter, positive otherwise.

Table 1. A(Hf) uncertainties, sensitivities to uncertainties in the atmospheric parameters, and partial uncertainties due to continuum placement and spectrum fit for the Hf II 3399 Å line, as well as the respective parameters ϕ , RW_{pure} , and RW_{min} , used for upper limit determination.

ID	$\sigma_{A(X)}$	$\sigma_{\Delta T_{\text{eff}}}$	$\sigma_{\Delta \log g}$	$\sigma_{\Delta [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]}$	$\sigma_{\Delta v_t}$	σ_c	σ_f	ϕ	RW_{pure}	RW_{min}
CES0031–1647	± 0.09	0.08	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.03	± 0.03	0.51	-5.47	-5.68
CES0045–0932	± 0.11	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.00	± 0.06	± 0.06	0.01	-6.34	-6.70
CES0048–1041	± 0.09	0.07	0.01	-0.01	-0.03	± 0.03	± 0.02	0.66	-5.30	-5.38
CES0055–3345	± 0.08	0.07	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.03	± 0.04	0.05	-5.55	-6.32
CES0059–4524	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0102–6143	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0107–6125	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0109–0443	± 0.14	0.08	0.01	0.00	-0.01	± 0.10	± 0.06	0.04	-5.83	-5.97
CES0215–2554	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.21	-6.01	-5.91
CES0221–2130	± 0.10	0.06	0.01	-0.02	-0.08	± 0.02	± 0.01	0.63	-5.06	-5.44
CES0242–0754	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0301+0616	± 0.14	0.08	0.01	0.01	-0.01	± 0.10	± 0.07	0.02	-5.92	-6.06
CES0338–2402	± 0.13	0.08	0.01	0.01	0.00	± 0.06	± 0.08	0.01	-6.48	-6.75
CES0413+0636	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0419–3651	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.14	-6.04	-5.91
CES0422–3715	± 0.11	0.08	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.06	± 0.06	0.04	-5.80	-6.19
CES0424–1501	± 0.45	0.04	0.01	-0.02	-0.44	± 0.05	± 0.01	0.68	-4.71	-5.12
CES0430–1334	± 0.16	0.07	0.01	-0.01	0.00	± 0.12	± 0.09	0.05	-6.24	-6.26
CES0444–1228	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0518–3817	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0527–2052	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0547–1739	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0747–0405	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0900–6222	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	1.65	-5.86	-4.05
CES0908–6607	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0919–6958	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1116–7250	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1221–0328	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1222+1136	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.41	-6.40	-5.88
CES1226+0518	± 0.09	0.07	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.05	0.03	-6.10	-6.74
CES1228+1220	± 0.09	0.08	0.01	-0.01	-0.04	± 0.03	± 0.01	0.33	-5.23	-5.69
CES1237+1922	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.18	-6.06	-5.73
CES1245–2425	± 0.15	0.08	0.01	-0.01	0.00	± 0.10	± 0.08	0.02	-6.18	-6.34
CES1322–1355	± 0.10	0.08	0.01	0.00	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.33	-5.69	-5.95
CES1402+0941	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1405–1451	± 0.26	0.04	0.01	-0.02	-0.26	± 0.03	± 0.03	0.91	-4.83	-5.16
CES1413–7609	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.72	-6.18	-5.37
CES1427–2214	± 0.09	0.08	0.01	0.00	0.01	± 0.02	± 0.04	0.02	-6.08	-6.96
CES1436–2906	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.01	-6.67	-6.51
CES1543+0201	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1552+0517	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.52	-6.30	-5.70
CES1732+2344	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1804+0346	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1942–6103	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2019–6130	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2103–6505	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2231–3238	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2232–4138	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2250–4057	± 0.16	0.08	0.01	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.11	± 0.07	0.04	-6.01	-6.05
CES2254–4209	± 0.13	0.07	0.01	0.01	-0.03	± 0.07	± 0.08	0.39	-5.33	-5.36
CES2330–5626	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.03	-6.02	-5.87
CES2334–2642	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

Table 2. A(Os) uncertainties, sensitivities to uncertainties in the atmospheric parameters, and partial uncertainties due to continuum placement and spectrum fit for the Os I 3301 Å line, as well as the respective parameters ϕ , RW_{pure} , and RW_{min} , used for upper limit determination.

ID	$\sigma_{A(X)}$	$\sigma_{\Delta T_{\text{eff}}}$	$\sigma_{\Delta \log g}$	$\sigma_{\Delta [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]}$	$\sigma_{\Delta v_t}$	σ_c	σ_f	ϕ	RW_{pure}	RW_{min}
CES0031–1647	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-6.50	-6.13
CES0045–0932	± 0.16	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.02	± 0.04	0.00	-6.13	-6.90
CES0048–1041	± 0.18	0.16	-0.01	0.01	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.06	0.00	-5.47	-6.04
CES0055–3345	± 0.17	0.15	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.08	0.00	-5.61	-6.17
CES0059–4524	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0102–6143	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0107–6125	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0109–0443	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0215–2554	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0221–2130	± 0.19	0.17	0.00	0.01	-0.01	± 0.05	± 0.08	0.00	-5.57	-6.06
CES0242–0754	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0301+0616	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0338–2402	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	0.01	0.00	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.00	-6.20	-6.66
CES0413+0636	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0419–3651	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-6.30	-6.05
CES0422–3715	± 0.19	0.15	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.10	± 0.06	0.00	-5.90	-6.06
CES0424–1501	± 0.16	0.14	0.00	0.01	-0.06	± 0.02	± 0.04	0.00	-5.17	-6.10
CES0430–1334	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-6.49	-6.25
CES0444–1228	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0518–3817	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0527–2052	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0547–1739	± 0.23	0.10	-0.01	0.04	-0.17	± 0.07	± 0.06	0.01	-4.89	-5.52
CES0747–0405	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0900–6222	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0908–6607	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0919–6958	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1116–7250	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1221–0328	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1222+1136	± 0.19	0.15	-0.01	0.00	0.01	± 0.05	± 0.10	0.00	-5.88	-6.33
CES1226+0518	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	-0.01	0.01	± 0.03	± 0.04	0.00	-6.04	-6.78
CES1228+1220	± 0.18	0.15	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.06	± 0.08	0.00	-5.74	-6.10
CES1237+1922	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1245–2425	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-6.42	-6.27
CES1322–1355	± 0.17	0.15	-0.01	0.00	-0.01	± 0.08	± 0.04	0.00	-5.87	-6.15
CES1402+0941	± 0.16	0.15	-0.01	0.01	0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.00	-5.81	-6.32
CES1405–1451	± 0.19	0.15	0.00	0.01	-0.10	± 0.01	± 0.03	0.00	-5.02	-6.16
CES1413–7609	± 0.20	0.17	-0.01	0.01	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.10	0.00	-5.66	-6.18
CES1427–2214	± 0.16	0.15	0.01	0.00	-0.01	± 0.02	± 0.04	0.00	-5.96	-6.76
CES1436–2906	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1543+0201	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1552+0517	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1732+2344	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1804+0346	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1942–6103	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2019–6130	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2103–6505	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2231–3238	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2232–4138	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2250–4057	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2254–4209	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2330–5626	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2334–2642	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

Table 3. A(Os) uncertainties, sensitivities to uncertainties in the atmospheric parameters, and partial uncertainties due to continuum placement and spectrum fit for the Os I 4420 Å line, as well as the respective parameters ϕ , RW_{pure} , and RW_{min} , used for upper limit determination.

ID	$\sigma_{A(X)}$	$\sigma_{\Delta T_{\text{eff}}}$	$\sigma_{\Delta \log g}$	$\sigma_{\Delta [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]}$	$\sigma_{\Delta v_t}$	σ_c	σ_f	ϕ	RW_{pure}	RW_{min}
CES0031–1647	± 0.19	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.09	± 0.06	0.00	-6.33	-6.51
CES0045–0932	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0048–1041	± 0.25	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.12	± 0.14	0.02	-6.41	-6.48
CES0055–3345	± 0.16	0.15	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.01	-5.94	-6.46
CES0059–4524	± 0.20	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.11	± 0.08	0.01	-6.20	-6.29
CES0102–6143	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0107–6125	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0109–0443	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0215–2554	± 0.17	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.07	± 0.02	0.00	-6.24	-6.58
CES0221–2130	± 0.18	0.17	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.03	± 0.04	0.02	-5.80	-6.53
CES0242–0754	± 0.19	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.07	± 0.06	0.02	-5.89	-6.19
CES0301+0616	± 0.20	0.14	0.00	-0.01	0.00	± 0.11	± 0.08	0.00	-6.20	-6.27
CES0338–2402	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0413+0636	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0419–3651	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0422–3715	± 0.16	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.01	-6.05	-6.56
CES0424–1501	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	-0.01	-0.03	± 0.02	± 0.02	0.04	-5.39	-6.30
CES0430–1334	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-7.36	-6.53
CES0444–1228	± 0.19	0.18	0.00	0.01	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.03	-5.53	-6.18
CES0518–3817	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0527–2052	± 0.26	0.17	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.12	± 0.16	0.01	-6.31	-6.36
CES0547–1739	± 0.16	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.08	± 0.02	± 0.01	0.10	-4.93	-5.94
CES0747–0405	± 0.22	0.09	0.00	0.01	-0.20	± 0.03	± 0.03	0.13	-4.72	-5.82
CES0900–6222	± 0.14	0.14	0.00	0.01	-0.02	± 0.02	± 0.03	0.05	-5.38	-6.18
CES0908–6607	± 0.21	0.20	0.01	0.02	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.06	0.02	-5.79	-6.33
CES0919–6958	± 0.20	0.20	-0.01	0.02	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.04	-5.51	-6.17
CES1116–7250	± 0.14	0.12	0.00	0.02	-0.02	± 0.02	± 0.07	0.05	-5.35	-6.33
CES1221–0328	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1222+1136	± 0.18	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.04	± 0.06	0.00	-6.29	-6.74
CES1226+0518	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1228+1220	± 0.17	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.07	± 0.03	0.01	-6.11	-6.41
CES1237+1922	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1245–2425	± 0.19	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.08	± 0.08	0.00	-6.31	-6.61
CES1322–1355	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-6.66	-6.52
CES1402+0941	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1405–1451	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1413–7609	± 0.18	0.17	0.00	0.01	0.01	± 0.04	± 0.03	0.01	-5.95	-6.43
CES1427–2214	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1436–2906	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1543+0201	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1552+0517	± 0.19	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.09	± 0.06	0.00	-6.29	-6.49
CES1732+2344	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-6.68	-6.51
CES1804+0346	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1942–6103	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2019–6130	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2103–6505	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2231–3238	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2232–4138	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-6.65	-6.38
CES2250–4057	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.01	-6.41	-6.40
CES2254–4209	± 0.17	0.16	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.02	-5.59	-6.18
CES2330–5626	± 0.17	0.15	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.06	0.01	-5.91	-6.37
CES2334–2642	± 0.17	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.05	± 0.04	0.01	-5.97	-6.38

Table 4. A(Ir) uncertainties, sensitivities to uncertainties in the atmospheric parameters, partial uncertainties due to continuum placement and spectrum fit for the Ir I 3513 Å line, as well as the respective parameters ϕ , RW_{pure} , and RW_{min} , used for upper limit determination. Stars whose IDs are marked with an asterisk had their upper limits set manually.

ID	$\sigma_{A(X)}$	$\sigma_{\Delta T_{\text{eff}}}$	$\sigma_{\Delta \log g}$	$\sigma_{\Delta [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]}$	$\sigma_{\Delta v_t}$	σ_c	σ_f	ϕ	RW_{pure}	RW_{min}
CES0031–1647	± 0.16	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.03	± 0.07	0.01	-5.61	-6.31
CES0045–0932	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.01	± 0.06	0.00	-6.02	-6.93
CES0048–1041	± 0.16	0.15	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.05	0.01	-5.37	-6.05
CES0055–3345	± 0.14	0.13	0.00	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.01	± 0.04	0.02	-5.70	-6.58
CES0059–4524	± 0.16	0.13	0.00	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.06	± 0.07	0.02	-5.61	-6.03
CES0102–6143	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0107–6125	± 0.28	0.12	0.00	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.11	± 0.22	0.01	-5.59	-5.72
CES0109–0443	± 0.17	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.11	± 0.05	0.00	-5.88	-6.02
CES0215–2554	± 0.18	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.08	± 0.08	0.00	-5.90	-6.17
CES0221–2130	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.02	± 0.05	0.04	-5.59	-6.40
CES0242–0754	± 0.16	0.13	-0.01	0.00	-0.03	± 0.05	± 0.07	0.01	-5.22	-5.76
CES0301+0616	± 0.24	0.12	0.01	0.01	0.01	± 0.11	± 0.17	0.00	-6.04	-6.16
CES0338–2402	± 0.30	0.13	0.00	-0.01	0.00	± 0.12	± 0.24	0.01	-6.63	-6.75
CES0413+0636	± 0.12	0.10	0.00	0.01	-0.06	± 0.03	± 0.03	0.06	-5.06	-5.91
CES0419–3651	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.01	-6.33	-6.27
CES0422–3715	± 0.17	0.13	0.00	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.10	± 0.06	0.01	-5.92	-6.10
CES0424–1501	± 0.10	0.09	0.01	-0.02	-0.03	± 0.01	± 0.04	0.13	-5.35	-6.52
CES0430–1334	± 0.18	0.13	0.00	-0.01	0.01	± 0.08	± 0.10	0.01	-6.02	-6.28
CES0444–1228	± 0.13	0.12	0.00	0.01	-0.04	± 0.03	± 0.04	0.03	-5.12	-5.89
CES0518–3817	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0527–2052	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.06	± 0.04	0.01	-5.42	-5.88
CES0547–1739	± 0.17	0.06	-0.01	0.01	-0.15	± 0.03	± 0.03	0.14	-4.86	-5.80
CES0747–0405	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0900–6222	± 0.10	0.06	0.00	0.01	-0.07	± 0.02	± 0.02	0.14	-5.05	-5.96
CES0908–6607	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0919–6958	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1116–7250	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1221–0328	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1222+1136*	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.01	-5.51	-6.60
CES1226+0518	± 0.13	0.13	0.00	-0.01	0.01	± 0.02	± 0.01	0.01	-5.97	-6.76
CES1228+1220	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.03	± 0.04	0.01	-5.52	-6.28
CES1237+1922	± 0.20	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.07	± 0.12	0.00	-5.85	-6.16
CES1245–2425	± 0.20	0.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	± 0.09	± 0.12	0.01	-6.24	-6.42
CES1322–1355	± 0.16	0.15	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.04	0.00	-5.84	-6.46
CES1402+0941*	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.01	-5.46	-6.51
CES1405–1451	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1413–7609	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.03	± 0.04	0.02	-5.50	-6.23
CES1427–2214	± 0.16	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.02	± 0.08	0.00	-5.77	-6.51
CES1436–2906	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.02	-7.11	-6.77
CES1543+0201	± 0.31	0.13	0.00	-0.01	0.01	± 0.15	± 0.24	0.01	-5.89	-5.90
CES1552+0517	± 0.17	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.04	± 0.10	0.01	-5.89	-6.51
CES1732+2344	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1804+0346	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1942–6103	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2019–6130	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2103–6505*	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.00	-5.79	-6.35
CES2231–3238	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2232–4138	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	0.01	-6.81	-5.95
CES2250–4057	± 0.15	0.14	0.00	-0.01	-0.01	± 0.04	± 0.02	0.00	-5.93	-6.50
CES2254–4209	± 0.15	0.13	0.00	0.00	-0.04	± 0.03	± 0.05	0.01	-5.16	-6.02
CES2330–5626	± 0.17	0.14	0.00	0.00	-0.01	± 0.07	± 0.08	0.00	-5.56	-5.96
CES2334–2642	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

Table 5. A(Pt) uncertainties, sensitivities to uncertainties in the atmospheric parameters, partial uncertainties due to continuum placement and spectrum fit for the Pt I 3301 Å line, as well as the respective parameters ϕ , RW_{pure} , and RW_{min} , used for upper limit determination.

ID	$\sigma_{A(X)}$	$\sigma_{\Delta T_{\text{eff}}}$	$\sigma_{\Delta \log g}$	$\sigma_{\Delta [\text{Fe}/\text{H}]}$	$\sigma_{\Delta v_t}$	σ_c	σ_f	ϕ	RW_{pure}	RW_{min}
CES0031–1647	± 0.11	0.10	0.00	0.00	–0.01	± 0.03	± 0.03	0.00	–5.33	–6.09
CES0045–0932	± 0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	–0.01	± 0.01	± 0.04	0.00	–5.37	–6.90
CES0048–1041	± 0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	–0.03	± 0.02	± 0.03	0.00	–5.09	–6.00
CES0055–3345	± 0.10	0.09	0.01	–0.01	–0.03	± 0.02	± 0.03	0.00	–5.22	–6.17
CES0059–4524	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0102–6143	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0107–6125	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0109–0443	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0215–2554	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0221–2130	± 0.10	0.08	0.01	–0.01	–0.03	± 0.02	± 0.02	0.01	–5.07	–6.01
CES0242–0754	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0301+0616	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0338–2402	± 0.11	0.10	0.01	0.00	–0.01	± 0.01	± 0.06	0.00	–5.59	–6.66
CES0413+0636	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0419–3651	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0422–3715	± 0.10	0.09	0.01	–0.01	–0.01	± 0.04	± 0.03	0.00	–5.36	–6.06
CES0424–1501	± 0.10	0.04	0.01	–0.02	–0.08	± 0.02	± 0.02	0.02	–4.88	–6.04
CES0430–1334	± 0.14	0.10	0.00	–0.01	–0.01	± 0.05	± 0.08	0.00	–5.68	–6.16
CES0444–1228	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0518–3817	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0527–2052	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0547–1739	± 0.21	–0.01	–0.02	0.05	–0.17	± 0.09	± 0.03	0.02	–4.79	–5.42
CES0747–0405	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0900–6222	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0908–6607	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES0919–6958	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1116–7250	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1221–0328	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1222+1136	± 0.09	0.08	0.00	0.00	–0.01	± 0.02	± 0.03	0.00	–5.36	–6.29
CES1226+0518	± 0.11	0.10	0.01	–0.01	–0.01	± 0.01	± 0.05	0.00	–5.48	–6.74
CES1228+1220	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1237+1922	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1245–2425	± 0.11	0.09	0.00	0.00	0.01	± 0.04	± 0.05	0.00	–5.60	–6.27
CES1322–1355	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1402+0941	± 0.08	0.07	0.00	0.00	–0.03	± 0.01	± 0.03	0.00	–5.15	–6.27
CES1405–1451	± 0.10	0.04	0.01	–0.01	–0.08	± 0.02	± 0.02	0.01	–4.88	–6.11
CES1413–7609	± 0.10	0.08	0.00	0.00	–0.03	± 0.02	± 0.03	0.00	–5.10	–6.13
CES1427–2214	± 0.10	0.10	0.00	0.00	–0.01	± 0.01	± 0.04	0.00	–5.37	–6.67
CES1436–2906	± 0.10	0.09	0.01	0.01	–0.02	± 0.01	± 0.04	0.00	–5.49	–6.73
CES1543+0201	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1552+0517	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1732+2344	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1804+0346	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES1942–6103	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2019–6130	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2103–6505	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2231–3238	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2232–4138	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2250–4057	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2254–4209	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2330–5626	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
CES2334–2642	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...